

Exploring The Medicinal Value of Vijaysara (*Pterocarpus Marsupium* ROXB.) From Nighantu

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ABSTRACT:

Background: *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) is an important drug described in various Ayurvedic Nighantu. It is mainly indicated in *Prameha*, *Medoroga*, *Kushtha*, *Raktapitta* and *Krimi*.

Material & Methods: Various Nighantu were reviewed to collect information regarding synonyms, *Rasapanchaka* and *Rogagnata* of *Vijaysara*.

Observations & Results: Different synonyms such as *Vijaysara*, *Asana*, *Beejak*, *Sarjaka*, *Mahasara* and *Peetasara* were observed in different Nighantu. *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) is described as having *Tikta-Kashaya Rasa*, *Ushna Veerya*, *Katu Vipaka* and *Kapha-Pittahara* property. It is indicated in *Prameha*, *Madhumeha*, *Medoroga*, *Kushtha*, *Raktapitta* and *Twakroga*.

Conclusion: Literary review of Ayurvedic Nighantu confirms that *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) possesses significant *Pramehaghna* and *Medohara* actions and plays an important role in the management of *Kapha* dominant disorders.

KEYWORD: Ayurveda, Nighantu, *Vijaysara*

INTRODUCTION

Vijaysara (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.), known in Ayurveda as *Vijaysara*, *Asana*, or *Beejaka*, is a revered medicinal tree mentioned in classical Nighantus and other Ayurvedic compendia as a potent therapeutic agent with diverse pharmacological properties. It belongs to the family Fabaceae (Leguminosae) and is widely distributed in the forests of India and Sri Lankaⁱ. where its heartwood and bark have been employed for centuries in the management of diabetes, inflammatory disorders, and various metabolic and degenerative conditions.ⁱⁱⁱIn ethnomedicinal uses leaves and gums are also used extensively for various conditions.ⁱⁱⁱ Modern phytochemical studies have validated these traditional claims by isolating bioactive constituents such as pterostilbene, epicatechin, marsupsin, and other polyphenolic compounds that exhibit antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, and cardioprotective activities.^{iv}

Exploring the medicinal value of Vijaysara from Nighantu, therefore, offers a structured bridge between classical Ayurvedic knowledge and contemporary evidence-based pharmacology, providing a scientific rationale for its use in chronic diseases such as diabetes, dyslipidemia, arthritis, and liver disorders, while also guiding standardization and rational clinical application of this important medicinal plant.

Table No. 1: Vernacular Name of Vijaysara (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.)

Description	Vijaysara ^v
Latin name	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> Roxb.
Family	Fabaceae
English name	Indian kino tree
Gujarati name	Biyo

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Information on *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) was compiled by reviewing 27 Ayurvedic Nighantu along with the e-Nighantu portal. The data were arranged in tabular form for better analysis and comparison of its synonyms, properties, and actions.

Observation:

Vijaysara is not described in 9 texts out of the 27 referred lexicons. The maximum number of synonyms are reported in Nighantu Shesha and Abhidhana Manjari. Most of the lexicons have classified *Vijaysara* under *Vatadi Varga*, as depicted in Table 1.

Table No. 1: References of Vijaysara (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) observed in various Nighantu.

Sr. No.	Nighantu	Author & Period	Gana	No. of synonyms	Abbreviation
1.	Sausruta Nighantu ^{vi}	Acharya Sushruta (5th century AD)	<i>Salasaradi Gana</i>	6 Synonyms	Su. Ni.
2.	Ashtanga Nighantu ^{vii}	Acharya Vahat (7th century AD)	<i>Asanadi Gana</i>	4 Synonyms	As. Ni.
3.	Amarakosha ^{viii}	Shrimad Amarsinha	<i>Vanaushadhi Varga</i>	6 Synonyms	A.K.
4.	Paryayaratna Mala ^{ix}	Madhavakara (9th century AD)	-	5 Synonyms	Pr. Rm.
5.	Siddhasara Nighantu ^x	Ravigupta (9th century AD)	-	3 Synonyms	Si.S.N
6.	Madanadi Nighantu ^{xi}	Acharya Chandranandana (10th century AD)	<i>Shodasa Gana</i>	9 Synonyms	Md. Ni.
7.	Dhanvantari Nighantu ^{xii}	Mahendra Bhaugika (10th -13th century AD)	<i>Amradi Varga</i>	9 Synonyms	D.N
8.	Dravyaguna Samgraha ^{xiii}	Acharya Chakrapanidatta (11th century AD)	-	Not mentioned	D.G.S.
9.	Shabda Chandrika ^{xiv}	Acharya Chakrapanidatta (11th century)	-	Not mentioned	S.C.

10.	Shodhala Nighantu ^{xv}	Acharya Shodhala (12 th century)	<i>Amradi Varga</i>	8 Synonyms	S.N.
11.	Nighantu Shesha ^{xvi}	Acharya Hemachandra (12 th century)	<i>Vrikshakanda</i>	17 Synonyms	Ni.S.
12.	Abhidhana Ratnamala ^{xvii}	(12 th -13 th century AD)	<i>KashayaSkandha</i>	8 Synonyms	Ab.Rm.
13.	Hridayadipika Nighantu ^{xviii}	Acharya Vopadeva (13 th century AD)	-	Not mentioned	Hr.Di.
14.	Madhava Dravyaguna ^{xix}	Acharya Madhav (13 th century)	-	Not mentioned	Ma.Dr.
15.	Siddhamantra ^{xx}	Vaidya Acharya Keshava (13 th century AD)	-	Not mentioned	Si.M.
16.	Madanapala Nighantu ^{xxi}	Acharya Madanapala (14 th century AD)	<i>Vatadi Varga</i>	5 Synonyms	M.N
17.	Kaiyadeva Nighantu ^{xxii}	Acharya Kaiyadeva (1425 AD)	<i>Aushadhi Varga</i>	11 Synonyms	K.D.
18.	Sarsavati Nighantu ^{xxiii}	16 th century AD	-	Not mentioned	Sa.Ni.
19.	Bhavaprakasha Nighantu ^{xxiv}	Acharya Bhavamishra (16 th century AD)	<i>Vatadi varga</i>	7 Synonyms	B.N.
20.	Raja Nighantu ^{xxv}	Narahari Pandit (17 th Century AD)	<i>Prabhadrdivarga</i>	8 Synonyms	R.N.
21.	Rajavallabha Nighantu ^{xxvi}	Shri Rajavallabha (18 th century)	-	Not mentioned	R.V.N.
22.	Laghu Nighantu ^{xxvii}	Vyasa Keshavarama (18 th century)	-	Not mentioned	L.N.
23.	Shaligrama Nighantu ^{xxviii}	Acharya Shaligrama (19 th century AD)	<i>Vatadi varga</i>	7 Synonyms	Sha.Ni.
24.	Abhidhanaa Manjari ^{xxix}	Acharya Bhashagacharya (1952 AD)	<i>Madanadi gana</i>	17 Synonyms	A.M.N.
25.	Priya Nighantu ^{xxx}	Acharya P.V. Sharma (20 th century AD)	-	3 Synonyms	P.N.
26.	Nighantu Adarsha ^{xxxi}	Bapalal Vaidya (20 th century AD)	-	7 Synonyms	N.A.
27.	Shivakosha ^{xxxii}	Shivadatta Mishra 1677 AD	-	Not mentioned	Si.K.

Synonyms of Vijaysara

Out of 27 *Nighantu*, synonyms of *Vijaysara (Pterocarpus marsupium Roxb.)* were found in 18 *Nighantu*. Total 42 synonyms were found for *Vijaysara (Pterocarpus marsupium Roxb.)* tabulated in table no. 2.

Table No. 2: Synonyms of *Vijaysara (Pterocarpus marsupium Roxb.)* observed in different *Nighantu*

Sr. No.	Synonyms	D.N	S.N	Ni.S	Ab.Rm	M.N	K.D	B.N	R.N	Sha.Ni	A.M.N	P.N	A.K.	N.A	A.N	Pr. Rm.	Si.S.N	M.d.Ni.	Su.Ni.
Based on Habitat																			
1.	<i>Sauri</i>	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Based on Morphology																			
1.	<i>Asana</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2.	<i>Mahasarja</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	<i>Tishya</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
4.	<i>Sugandhi</i>	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
5.	<i>Pitasalaka</i>	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
6.	<i>Peetsara</i>	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
7.	<i>Pitaka</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
8.	<i>Krushnasarjak</i>	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	<i>Krishnavriksha</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	<i>Krishnasara</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	<i>Kharasara</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	<i>Nilaka</i>	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
13.	<i>Suneel</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14.	<i>Nilakantha</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
15.	<i>Bandhukapuspa</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
16.	<i>Beejak</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+
17.	<i>Kamya</i>	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18.	<i>Neel niryasa</i>	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
19.	<i>Pushpavruksha</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20.	<i>Sarjak</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
21.	<i>Alakapriya</i>	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

22	Syama	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	Priyashalaka	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
24	Priya	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
25	Gauro	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
26	Mahasala	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
27	Tiryapushpa	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
28	Bijavrksa	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29	Bijahva	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
30	Tishyavruksha	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
31	Vasantapushpka	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
32	Kshetrapushpa	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
33	Vimsakapuspaka	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
34	Krushtavruksha	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
35	Pushpavriksha	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
36	Kosya	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
37	Asirastatha	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Based on Properties and Action

1.	Karshya	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Priyaka	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
3.	Jivak	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
4.	Kalyana	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total		9	8	16	8	5	11	7	8	7	17	3	6	7	4	5	3	9	6

Table No. 3: Nirukti of Vijaysara (Pterocarpus marsupium Roxb.) Synonyms^{xxxiii}

No.	Synonym	Nirukti	Meaning
1.	शौरिः	शूरे शूरसेनप्रदेशे भवः ।	Beejak commonly grows in Shura sena pradesha (Western Uttar Pradesh).
2.	पीवरः	स्थूल काण्डत्वात् ।	Trunk of Beejak is very large.
3.	महासर्ज	महान् वृक्षः सर्जाकारः ।	Beejak is big tree like that of Sarja (Vateria indica).
4.	तिष्यः	तिष्ये पौष्यमासे पुष्यति ।	Beejak blossoms in Pushya masa (Late winter).
5.	सुगन्धि	पुष्याणां सुगन्धित्वात् ।	Flowers are aromatic.

6.	पीतसारः	पीतवर्णः सरोऽस्य ।	Heart wood of <i>Beejak</i> is yellow in colour.
7.	पीतशालकः	पीतसारः शालसदृशः ।	Heart wood is yellow in colour and resembles heart wood of <i>Sala</i> (<i>Shorea robusta</i>).
8.	कार्श्यं	कृशत्वजनकः ।	<i>Beejak</i> is <i>Karshyakara</i> . (emaciating)
9.	असन	-	Its seeds are enclosed within a covering (seed coat).
10.	बीजक	-	Its fruit is mainly seed-dominant in nature.
11.	गौर	-	Powder of its heartwood is applied externally to enhance fair complexion.
12.	प्रियक	-	Due to its scraping (<i>Lekhana</i>) property, it is beneficial and <i>Priya</i> (useful) in persons suffering from obesity (<i>Medoroga</i>).
13.	नीलनिर्यास	-	When its heartwood is soaked in water overnight, the water develops a bluish tinge. Its exudate (resin) is also bluish in color.
14.	नीलक	-	Because of this blue colored exudate, it is called <i>Neelaka</i> . Synonyms of <i>Neela</i> (blue) are also used for it.
15.	बीजवृक्ष	-	It is a tree whose fruits are seed-dominant.
16.	तिष्यवृक्ष	-	The tree flowers during the month of <i>Tishya</i> (Pausha – late winter season).
17.	बन्धूकपुष्प	-	Its flowers resemble those of <i>Bandhooka</i> (<i>Hibiscus hirtus</i> L.).
18.	कृष्णसर्जक	-	Refers to the dark-colored exudate (gum) the tree produces.
19.	कृष्णवृक्ष	-	Refers to the dark timber or the dark streaks in the wood.
20.	कृष्णसार	-	Indicates that the Heartwood (essence) is dark in color.
21.	खरसार	-	Describes the hard, dense, and slightly rough texture of the wood.
22.	सुनील	-	Emphasizes the deep blue color created when the wood is soaked.
23.	नीलकण्ठ	-	A poetic comparison, like the blue throat of Shiva or a peacock.
24.	पुष्पवृक्ष	-	A tree known for its distinct and beautiful flowering.
25.	सर्जक	-	A general term for trees that produce resin or sarja.
26.	जीवक	-	Highlights its medicinal role in rejuvenating health.
27.	अलकप्रिय	-	<i>Alaka</i> can mean bees; they are attracted to its nectar.
28.	श्यामा	-	Refers to the dark, brownish-black color of the heartwood.
29.	प्रियशालक	-	Describes the attractive structure of its branches.

30.	महाशाल	-	Categorizes it as a large, sturdy tree similar to the Sal tree.
31.	वसन्तपुष्पक	-	Indicates that the tree flowers during the spring season.
32.	क्षेत्रपुष्प	-	it is found in specific regions/fields (habitats).
33.	कल्याण	-	Refers to its welfare-giving medicinal properties.
34.	विशकपुष्पक	-	Likely a botanical reference to the grouping of its flowers.
35.	कोश्य	-	Possibly refers to the seed pod which acts like a sheath (Kosha).

Rasapanchaka and Doshagnata of Vijaysara (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.)

Out of 27 Nighantu, *Rasapanchaka* of *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) is described in Dhanvantari Nighantu, KaiyadevaNighantu, Raja Nighantu, Priya Nighantu and Nighantu Adarsha. Among them, the difference of opinion observed as mentioned in below table no. 3.

Table No. 4: Rasapanchaka and Doshagnata of Vijaysara

Sr. No.	Text	Rasa			Veerya		Vipaka	Doshagnata		
		Tikta	Katu	Kashya	Ushna	Shita	Katu	Kaphahara	Vatahara	Pittahara
1.	M.N.	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
2.	D.N.	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
3.	K.N.	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
4.	B.N.	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
5.	R.N.	+	+		+	-	-	-	+	-
6.	S.N.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	P.N.	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
8.	N.A	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+
Total		2	3	4	3	1	1	5	1	5

Rogagnata:

After reviewing 27 Nighantu, *Rogagnata* of *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) were observed in 6 Nighantu are tabulated in table no. 4.

Table No. 4: Rogagnata of Vijaysara (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) observed in various Nighantu

Sr. No.	Rogagnata	D.N.	M.N.	K. N	B.N	R. N	P.N.
1.	<i>Raktapitta</i>	-	-	+	+	-	+
2.	<i>Krimi</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-
3.	<i>Visharp</i>	-	+	+	+	-	-
4.	<i>Kushtha</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+
5.	<i>Switra</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-
6.	<i>Medoroga</i>	-	-	+	-	-	-
7.	<i>Prameha</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+
8.	<i>Vrana</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-
9.	<i>Jvara</i>	-	+	-	-	-	-
10.	<i>Galaroga</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
11.	<i>Raktamandala</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-
Total		5	6	7	6	2	3

Table No. 5: Karma of Vijaysara (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb) Observed in different Nighantu

No	Karma	R.N	P.N	M.N	B.N	K.N
1.	Saraka	+	-	-	-	-
2.	Stambhana	-	+	-	-	-
3.	Keshya	-	-	+	+	+
4.	Twachya	-	-	+	-	+
5.	Rasayana	-	-	+	+	-

DISCUSSION

This review systematically evaluates the classical descriptions of *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) across 27 Ayurvedic Nighantus, focusing on its synonyms, physicochemical properties, and therapeutic indications. A total of 42 synonyms and 14 therapeutic actions were documented across the reviewed literature. Notably, the drug is absent in nine Nighantus, including Dravyaguna Samgraha, Sabda Chandrika, Hridayadipika, Madhava Dravyaguna, Siddhamantra, Sarasvati, Rajavallabha, Laghu Nighantu, and the works of Shivadatta Mishra. Among the recorded texts, frequently cited synonyms such as *Asana*, *Beejak*, *Mahasarja*, *Sauri*, and *Bandhukapuspa* reflect strong inter textual consensus in botanical identification. Considerable variation is observed in *Varga* wise classification across classical Nighantus ranging from *Salasaradi Gana* (Sushruta Nighantu), *Asanadi Gana* (Ashtanga Nighantu) and *Amradi Varga* (Dhanvantari Nighantu, Shodhala Nighantu) to *Vatadi Varga*, as consistently recorded in Madanapala, Bhavaprakasha, and Shaligrama Nighantu. Acharya Chandranandana describes it within the *Madanadi (Shodasa) Gana*, while Abhidhana Ratnamala places it under *Kashaya Skandha*. Raja Nighantu, authored by Narahari Pandit, classifies it in *Prabhardadi Varga*, and Bapalal Vaidya includes it under *Palasadi Varga* in Nighantu Adarsha. Lexicographic texts including Amarakosha, Nighantu Shesha, and Abhidhana Manjari further attest its recognition across *Vanaushadhi Varga*, *Vrikshakanda*, and *Madanadi Gana* respectively. This divergence in classification reflects the textual evolution and regional scholarly traditions inherent to Ayurvedic Nighantu literature. From this observed classification in lexicon, it can be said that everyone made classification based on nature of drug i.e. tree. As per importance of the plant group or *Varga* is named by the author of the lexicons.

Considerable inter-textual variation is also observed in *Rasapanchaka*. *Tikta Rasa* is described in Raja Nighantu and Nighantu Adarsha, whereas *Katu* and *Kashaya Rasa* are predominantly reported in Kaiyadeva Nighantu and Nighantu Adarsha. *Shita Virya* and *Katu Vipaka* remain confined to Priya Nighantu and Nighantu Adarsha. In contrast, *Doshagnata* exhibits relatively better inter-textual concordance, with predominant *Kaphahara* activity frequently accompanied by *Pittahara* action, while *Vatahara* properties are least emphasized, indicating a consistent classical therapeutic orientation toward *Kapha* and *Pitta* disorders. Therapeutically, *Vijaysara* is primarily indicated for *Krimighna*, *Kusthaghna*, *Svitraghna*, *Pramehaghna*, and *Vranaropana* activities, while limited indications are reported for *Keshya*, *Raktapitta*, *Medoroga*, *Rasayana*, and *Jvara* collectively reflecting a selective Pharmacological profile. Variable *Karma* including *Saraka* action as described in Raja Nighantu and *Stambhana* action in Priya Nighantu, further suggests context-dependent pharmacological behaviour across classical traditions. From a conservation standpoint, *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb. faces a severe demand-supply imbalance, with high commercial demand far exceeding natural availability, resulting in overexploitation and significant population decline. The species is currently categorized under various threatened statuses across India, underscoring urgent conservation concern. These findings collectively affirm the classical significance of *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb. and highlight the pressing need for its conservation through sustainable harvesting practices and evidence-based utilization strategies.

CONCLUSION

This review Highlights both consistency and variation in the classical descriptions of *Vijaysara* (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.) across 27 Ayurvedic Nighantus. Despite its absence in nine texts, the drug demonstrates strong inter textual agreement in *Doshagnata*, predominantly exhibiting *Kaphahara* and *Pittahara* actions. The diverse Varga wise classification, ranging from *Salasaradi Gana* (Sushruta Nighantu) and *Asanadi Gana* (Ashtanga Nighantu) to *Amradi Varga* (Dhanvantari Nighantu), *Vatadi Varga* (Bhavaprakasha, Madanapala, Shaligrama Nighantu), and *Aushadhi Varga* (Kaiyadeva Nighantu), Reflects the textual evolution and regional scholarly traditions inherent to Ayurvedic Nighantu literature rather than any fundamental disagreement in drug identity. Variations observed in *Rasa*, *Virya* and *Vipaka* similarly represent interpretative differences among classical authors. Therapeutically, *Vijaysara* is consistently indicated for *Krimighna*, *Kusthaghna*, *Svitraghna*, *Pramehaghna*, and *Vranaropana* activities, suggesting a selective and well-defined pharmacological profile. These findings collectively provide a coherent classical foundation for further experimental and clinical validation of *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb.

REFERENCES

1. Mahakal N, Gulhane H. Review article on Vijaysar (*Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb): A multidimensional herb. AYUSHDHARA. 2022;9(2):138.
2. Dhayaney V, Sibi G. *Pterocarpus marsupium* for the treatment of diabetes and other disorders. *J Complement Med Alt Healthcare*. 2019;9(1):555754. doi:10.19080/JCMAH.2019.09.555754
3. Rahman MS, Mujahid M, Siddiqui MA, Rahman MA, Arif M, Eram S, et al. Ethnobotanical uses, phytochemistry and pharmacological activities of *Pterocarpus marsupium*: a review. *Pharmacogn J*. 2018;10(6 Suppl):S1-S8.
4. Chothe K, Phadtare G, Kamble S, Sirvi H, Arote S. *Pterocarpus marsupium*: An ethnopharmacological treasure with emerging clinical relevance. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2026;4(2):Article ID IJPS/260402057.
5. <https://efloraofindia.com/efi/pterocarpus-marsupium>

6. Acharya Sushruta, Sausruta Nighantu, E-book, designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015
7. Acharya Vahata, Ashtanga Nighantu, E-book, designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 201
8. Amarasimha, Edited by dr.Bhrahmananda Tripathi Amarakosha. Dwitiyakanda vanaushadhivarga, ver. 44. Chaukhamba vidhyabhavan Varanasi; Edition 2011.
9. Indukarsunu Madhav, Paryayaratnamala, E-book, designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015.
10. Siddhasara Nighantu, E-book, designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015
11. Anonymous, Madanadi Nighantu, E-book, designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015.
12. Dr. Zarkhande oza, Dr. Umapati Mishra, editors, Mahendra Bhaugik, Dhanvantari Nighantu (with Hindi Gunakarmatmaka commentary). Amradi Varga, Vers- 126, Reprint. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashana;
13. Acharya Chakrapanidatta, Dravyagunasamgraha, E-book, designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015
14. Acharya Chakrapanidatta, Shabdachandrika, E-book. designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015.
15. Prof. Gyanendra Pandey commentator, Prof. R. R. Dwiwedi editor, Vaidyacharya Shodhala, Sodhala Nighantu (Namasamgraha and Gunasamgraha).Amradi Varga Ver. 608 1 st edition, 2009. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy.
16. Acharya Hemachandra, Nighantushesha, E-book. designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. pratham vrukshakanda, Ver.99 -101. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015.
17. Prof. P. V. Sharma, editor. Abhidhana Ratnamala.Shashtha Skandha, ver-81, Reprint. Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2015.
18. Acharya Keshava, Hridaydeepakanighantu, E-book. designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. dwinama varga, Ver. 113. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015
19. Dr. C.Murali Krishna, Dr. S.Pavan Kumar English translation by Dr. A.Narayana Madhava Dravyaguna, Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy Edition-First,2012
20. <https://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/e-Nighantu/siddhamantra/?mod=search&search>.
21. Pd. Harihara prasada Tripathi, editor, Madan, Madanapal Nighantu (with Hindi Commentary entitled Hari). Vatadi Varga, ver.34-35. 1st edition 2009, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy.
22. Prof. P. V. Sharma, Dr. Guruprasad Sharmas, editor and translator, Kaiyadeva, Kaiyadeva Nighantu. Aushadhi Varga; Ver. 811-814. Reprint 2016. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; p. 151.
23. Anonymous, Saraswati nighantu, edited by Dr. S. D. Kamat, 1st Edition. Delhi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishtan; 2006.
24. 4 Prof. K.C. Chunekar, Commentator, Late Dr. G.S. Pandey, editor, Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakasha Nighantu.Vatadi Varga, Ver. 28-29, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharati Academy; 2015.
25. Narhari pandit, Raja Nighantu, edited by Dr. Satish Chandra Sankhyadhar, Dr. Deepika Sankhyakadhar, forward by Prof. K.C. Chunekar. Prabhadradi Varga, Ver. 132-133, p.463. Reprint edition, Varanasi: Chowkhambha Orientalia, 2017.

26. Acharya Rajvallabha, Rajvallabha Nighantu, E-book. designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015.
27. Vyasa Keshavaram, Laghu Nighantu, E-book. designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad, New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS), 2015 vers.126-127
28. Shri Shaligramvaishyavarya, Shaligrama Nighantu Bhushana, Brihat Nighantu Ratnakar. Part 7-8, vatadi varga. Reprint 2011, Mumbai: Khemaraja Shrikrishnadas Prakashana; p. 503.
29. Bhishagacharya, Abhidhanmanjari, Sankirna Varga, ver-1066, E-book. designed and developed by National Institute of Indian Medical Heritage (NIIMH), Hyderabad. New Delhi: Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS); 2015.
30. Prof. Priyavrat Sharma, Priya Nighantu. Haritkyadi Varga, Ver. 127-128. Reprint, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan; Edition 2004; p. 29.
31. Shri Bapalal Vaidya, Nighantu Adarsha, Vol-1, Palasadi Varga, Reprint. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Bharati Academy;2016; p.381.
32. <https://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/e-Nighantu/shivakosha/?mod=read>
33. Hegde PL, Harini A. A Text Book of Dravyaguna Vijnana. Vol. II. New Delhi: Chaukhambha Publications; 2019.